

Consumer Behaviour is More Than Just Buying Things. It's About Understanding the Complex Interplay of Psychology, Economics, Culture, And Environment That Drives Human Choices

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Abstract— The growing market for beauty serums, especially on online shopping websites such as Nykaa, offers a strong research case to study consumer repurchase behavior. This research examines the drivers of consumers' loyalty towards certain serum brands, with specific emphasis on the efficacy of Korean beauty serums and the importance of ingredient transparency. The study utilizes a quantitative approach, conducting a survey of 100 participants made up mainly of young women, a group that accounts for a large part of the serum market. Key takeaways indicate that 67% of consumers focus on product efficacy when making purchasing decisions, while 51% consider ingredients, showing a turn towards ingredient-driven purchasing habits. The findings also indicate that 37% of respondents buy serums every 2-3 months, showing moderate devotion to serum consumption and indicating the development of brand loyalty. Most importantly, 55% of consumers prefer buying online, indicating the vital role of ecommerce in the beauty sector. Even though brands such as Dot & Key and L'Oréal enjoy popularity, according to the research, 60% of the respondents have never used Korean serums and are also indifferent to their effectiveness, with 36.7% viewing them as a fleeting trend. This lack of trust is a challenge to K-beauty brands that need to present strong evidence of their product's effectiveness in order to change consumer attitudes. In addition, before-and-after outcome importance, highly rated by 57% of participants, shows the necessity to boost consumer faith by making strategies more transparent and open. Solving this research issue is essential because not only does it enrich the knowledge about consumer behaviour within the beauty segment, but also offers practical solutions for brands willing to boost market presence and cultivate consumer loyalty. Through an analysis of repurchase intentions, the present study tries to inform marketing strategies that would appeal to changing consumer preferences within the serum sector.

Keywords: Consumer behaviour, brand loyalty, skincare market, women, repurchases.

INTRODUCTION

From the last so many years, the beauty and skincare industry has gone through multiple changes and a major transformation by witnessing the emergence of online selling platforms like Nykaa, which has manipulated the ways consumers purchased the products. Among the kaleidoscope of products that are found available online and offline, skincare serums have emerged as my favourite personally. Well my fascination with skincare products has been a very personal and overwhelming journey of well being that made me aware about multiple facts that states why skin care should be included in everyone's daily regime. Since I am a very profound user when it comes to skin care, my skin has been observing very subtle and healthy changes since I have added the use of serums in my regime according to my skin type.

The constant admiration for the same made me wonder about the broader perspective regarding the consumer behaviour in the skin care industry, after noticing the constant trend of repurchasing same serums by consumers on Nykaa. Despite the increasing demand of serums, there remains a lack of holistic comprehension about the factors or unseen points that leads customers to repurchase the products on platforms like Nykaa. Also there are no significant answers about if Korean beauty serums are genuinely worth the use or not. Now the question that strikes my head is - what is that top most thing that turns customers so loyal towards a particular brand or product? Korean beauty products especially serums have taken over instagram completely which makes it an interesting question to talk about! The ingredients in those products promise transformative results.

Since Korean beauty products are in so much demand, the question that arises now is , are Korean beauty serums just a

part of trend or are they really worth the hype that has been taking over the whole market. In addition to knowing what specific ingredients are being used in the serums that particularly enhance the product performance in the market and how ratings and reviews justify it. These questions form the foundation of my research and will focus on repurchasing habits of consumers considering varying factors, with a particular highlight on the effectiveness of Korean beauty serums and the ingredients, review and ratings of how they are seen and understood by the customers. The limitations may include the massive changes of the beauty trends that may or may not affect the existence of the findings and collections over the time. The major motive of this study is to understand the aspects that regulate the consumer repurchasing behaviour for serums, this is important for the brand companies that focus on building trust and loyalty with their users and to understand how to make customers satisfied so that they will stick to the company for considerably long years. By scrutinizing the result rate of Korean beauty serums and how the variety of ingredients used in skin care products perform, this study will provide clear insights for consumers and brand companies. This research aims to fill the gaps between the expectations of customers and the performance of products by nurturing an informed and satisfactory shopping experience on platforms like Nykaa.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Repurchase by consumers of facial serums on e-retailers like Nykaa is guided by a constellation of psychological, functional, and social drivers. Positive platform and product attitudes, guided by trust in retailer credibility and signal quality, are the foundation of loyalty (Huong et al., 2024; PubMed, 2024). Perceived product quality is also crucial, as it enhances customer satisfaction and mediates repeat purchase (Selvia, Yacob, & Lubis, 2024; ResearchGate, 2024). Equitable prices and perceived value also strengthen repurchase behavior because consumers evaluate prices in relation to tangible results (Moslehpour, Wong, Pham, & Aulia, 2018). Korean beauty serums (K-beauty) demonstrate the way new actives and next-generation delivery systems can turn trend into long-term loyalty: peptides, hyaluronic acid, vitamin C, and microencapsulation technologies convey visible benefits which fans endorse with word-of-mouth and online commentary (Lee & Kim, 2022; Vogue Business, 2021). Third-party experts and user-generated review trust indications serve also as powerful drivers both for the initial tries and final repurchases (IJREHC, 2024; Cyntya & Berlianto, 2022).

Most repurchase intention behavior for skincare can be accounted for through theory of planned behavior. Through

cross-sectional data obtained on consumers of Vietnam, attitude toward product provided a contribution rate to 27.5 % to explain repurchase behavior variation following that from retailer credibility and quality of signals (Huong et al., 2024). These "signals" include comprehensive ingredient lists, ingredient-filter features, and open sourcing information, all of which lower perceived risk and enhance purchase confidence (PubMed, 2024). On Nykaa, where counterfeiting concerns are high, repeated positive encounters with delivery, authenticity assurance, and customer support enhance trust, rendering repeat visits a matter of habit (Selvia et al., 2024). Additionally, price equity—obtained via open pricing, loyalty reward points, and packaged deals—increases perceived value and solidifies the consumer's reordering decision (Moslehpour et al., 2018).

K-beauty's whirlwind popularity was first driven by social media buzz and influencer marketing (Smith, 2025). However, research indicates that trendiness alone cannot be maintained as a basis of loyalty. WOM in Taiwan, price fairness in perception, and country-of-origin prestige were the best predictors of K-beauty repeat purchase, but the most significant variable was WON (Moslehpour et al., 2018; GrowKudos, 2025). Indonesian research into Korean serum consumers also found packaging appeal, attitude towards consumption, and peer influence (subjective norms) to be key repeat-buy drivers (Utami & Wijaya, 2024). Therefore, K-beauty's longevity is a result of its blend of effective formulation, robust peer endorsement, and perceived status, not fleeting hype.

At the heart of both international and Kbeauty serum success are active ingredients of note. Hyaluronic acid, which can retain more than 1,000 times its weight in water, provides instant plumping and hydration, and is a consistent best-seller (Allied Market Research, 2024). Vitamin C serums in 15– 23 % concentrations are clinical-grade antioxidants that brighten and collagen-stimulate skin, often gracing "best of" lists (NY Post, 2025). Peptides—short chains of amino acids—send a message to synthesize collagen and smooth fine lines with time (MarketResearchFuture, 2024). Retinol and its milder precursor retinal increase cell turnover and can visibly decrease wrinkles (Allure, 2025). Niacinamide strengthens the skin barrier, controls sebum, and even tone (Grand View Research, 2024). The shift in consumers towards "sky intellectualism" means most now buy based on ingredient over brand, applying filters on Nykaa and other platforms to customize serums for certain issues (Chitrakorn, 2021).

In addition to ingredients themselves, contemporary delivery systems optimize serum effectiveness. Liposomes, niosomes, microspheres, and ethosomes package activities for enhanced dermal penetration and long-term release (Lee & Kim, 2022;

ResearchGate, 2022). Exposures of multifunctional delivery platforms reveal that such carriers possess the potential to enhance bioavailability by as high as 40 %, contributing to faster and more perceivable outcomes (Lee & Kim, 2022). Therefore, companies that engage in exclusive encapsulation technologies gain a differentiation point, creating the value proposition, which triggers purchasing again.

Both online ratings and reviews act as key trust drivers that determine not only trial, but also repurchase. In Jabodetabek, esteemed reviews increased brand value and customer satisfaction, thereby impacting repurchase intention for a local beauty laboratory (Cyntya & Berlianto, 2022). Review valence, perceived credibility, and review volume were found to have strong positive impacts on purchases of skin care in the Philippines (Maricar et al., 2023). Shoppers claim to check both user-generated reviews on Nykaa and expert-curated reviews on third-party websites (e.g., BeautyCheck, CosDNA) prior to ordering their preferred serums (Andersson, 2021; IJREHC, 2024). High review credibility—with balanced pros and cons, checked purchases, and real-user images—also supports the perceived trustiness of opinions (IJREHC, 2024).

The interaction of these variables establishes a feedback cycle: effective systems and ingredients produce good results; happy customers leave positive comments; new consumers believe those comments and use the product; many become repeat consumers. Retailers and brands such as Nykaa that allow this cycle to be enabled—via clear information, review-filtering capabilities, and effective post-purchase support—solidify loyalty from consumers and fuel high repeat-buy rates.

Overall, Nykaa repurchase of serums is not a chance occurrence but the result of well-established mechanisms: robust product attitudes, faith in retailer credibility, stable product quality, reasonable prices, innovative activities and delivery systems, and trustworthy online reviews. Korean beauty serums are a case study in how constant innovation in ingredients and peer endorsement can convert social media buzz into long-term loyalty. For researchers and practitioners alike, attention to these interconnected variables provides a clear blue-print for understanding—and improving— consumer repurchase behavior in the competitive skincare industry.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research has found its base in a quantitative research design to know about the factors that influence the customers to repurchase a product specifically a serum and their behaviour towards the Nykaa platform, particularly focusing on Korean

beauty products. The quantitative approach is opted for its capability to provide measurable and statistically analysable data, that allows the researcher to develop a clear understanding of the preferences made by the customer and the behaviour attached. The study aims to collect numerical data that can be analysed to identify trends, patterns attached to customer behaviour specifically regarding the effectiveness of ingredients and brand loyalty. The sample size for this study is a set of 100 participants, which is marked sufficient to provide a representative overview of customer behaviour in terms of buying serums on Nykaa. I have used a Snowball sampling method to gather data by keeping in mind the base of my research. This non probability sampling method is particularly useful in accessing the areas that are difficult to reach or connect to by using traditional methods.

A small group of 100 people who use nykaa to buy serums or other platforms too will be identified, the former participants will then refer the questionnaire to other people who seems like a perfect fit for the criteria, thereby making a web of networks to collect samples. This technique plays a very dramatically influential role in the beauty and skincare industry, where customer preferences and suggestions or recommendations play an important role in decision making.

Data was collected through an online survey, which was distributed to participants through social media platforms like whatsapp and telegram. The survey was created keeping in mind the objective based questions which was created to collect quantitative data on various aspects that influence consumer behaviour, which includes brand loyalty, ingredients preferred, perceptions about the Korean beauty serums. The survey also carried questions that were designed to measure how customers react towards a particular brand and ingredient, and how much satisfied with their serum purchase. This method allows collection of data on a large heterogeneous scale providing a wider and broader range of responses, which makes sure we get somehow accurate representation of consumer opinions and their individual experiences.

After the data has been collected, it shall be analyzed utilizing cohort analysis methodology. Cohort analysis entails categorizing the data into groups characterized by commonality, for instance, age, gender, or buying frequency. The method shall facilitate the tracing of trends and patterns within specified consumer groups in a way that will give clearer insight into what different demographics understand and engage with serum products in Nykaa. Statistical software like SPSS or R will be used to conduct descriptive and inferential statistical analysis, such as frequency distributions, cross-tabulations, and correlation analysis. These analyses will assist

in establishing the relationship between different factors, such as ingredient effectiveness and intention to repurchase, thus answering the research questions of this study. Ethical concerns will be of great importance at all stages of the study.

The participants will be informed about the reason for the study and will give their consent prior to participating. Anonymity and confidentiality will be guaranteed, with no personal information collected in the survey. Participants will also have the freedom to withdraw from the study at any point without any consequences. Through the observance of ethical research standards, the research seeks to maintain the integrity of the data gathered and the validity of the results. Ethical issues will be of utmost concern throughout all stages of the study. Participants will be made aware of why the study is being conducted and will provide consent before contributing. Anonymity and confidentiality will be ensured with no identification information gathered through the survey. Participants will also be free to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. By upholding ethical research practice, the study attempts to uphold the validity of findings and the integrity of data collected.

While this research methodology is intended to provide meaningful insights into consumer behavior toward serums on Nykaa, acknowledging potential limitations is essential. The application of snowball sampling could introduce bias because participants can forward the survey to others with similar characteristics or opinions, which could warp the results. Moreover, the use of self-reported data can cause inaccuracies because participants might not always give truthful or reflective answers. In addition, the emphasis on a single e-commerce site may restrict the applicability of the findings to other retailing contexts. Regardless of these constraints, the adopted research method should provide insightful findings about consumer attitudes and behavior that would advance knowledge of drivers of repurchase intention of serums within the beauty segment.

Overall, this research approach maps a systematic procedure for conducting consumer behavior analysis on serums within Nykaa. Through a quantitative design, the use of a snowball sampling method, and data analysis using cohort analysis, the research seeks to gain an in-depth appreciation of the determinants of consumer repurchase behavior, especially among K-beauty products. The research findings will not only add to the body of knowledge academically but also provide applied implications for brands that need to strengthen marketing strategies and product promotion in the beauty industry.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

The information gathered through the survey is a wealth of information in understanding the purchasing behavior of serum on Nykaa among the 18-25 age group. From the analysis, certain trends and likings emerge which can guide the marketing approach as well as product development of beauty companies.

The examination of the survey findings presents a set of critical findings to the research goals:

- **Demographic Analysis:** The majority of the survey participants are young women, and thus this group is an essential market segment for serum products. Those brands that are appealing to this particular age group can capture the chance to provide targeted marketing approaches appealing to their values and interests.
- **Buying Frequency :** The data shows that a large proportion of customers (37%) purchases serums every 2-3 months, indicating a moderate level of commitment towards the use of serum. This frequency indicates that consumers will likely be repeat buyers, and this is a key requirement for brand loyalty.
- **Online Shopping Preference:** The 55% online buying preference for serums highlights the role of e-retailers such as Nykaa in the beauty space. Therefore, companies need to concentrate on making their online presence felt and making the shopping process easier to maintain the trend.
- **Deciding Factors:** The fact that 67% of the respondents look at product effectiveness as a deciding factor indicates the significance of product performance in determining consumer loyalty. Secondly, the 29% of the respondents who consider ingredients first indicate the trend of ingredient-based buying; therefore, the efficacy of the formulations must be highlighted by brands.
- **Brand Preferences:** That L'Oréal and Dot & Key serums are the most preferred among the respondents indicates the success of these brands in establishing a strong market presence. The reasons for these brands' popularity can be very helpful to other brands that want to improve their market position.
- **Ingredients' Significance:** The fact that 51% of the respondents named the ingredients as the most important feature indicates that brands need to be more transparent and give more informative content about their compositions. The popularity and common understanding of ingredients such as niacinamide, hyaluronic acid, and vitamin C indicate that brands that use these ingredients in their compositions can get an edge over others.

- **Korean Serums Perception:** The finding that 60% of the respondents were never users of Korean serums and were neutral about their usefulness signifies the presence of a barrier to mass acceptance of K-beauty brands in the group. The finding that 36.7% of the individuals view Korean serums as a trend also signifies that brands need to present strong evidence of their usefulness in an effort to alter consumer perception.
- **Importance of Results:** The fact that 57% of the respondents value results before and after applying serum indicates that firms should provide genuine testimonials from actual consumers, photo and video proof attesting to the effectiveness of their products. These steps can enhance customer confidence and, in turn, sales of the product.

The results of this survey provide a direct answer to the research questions developed in this study:

1. What are the drivers of consumer loyalty and repurchase intent towards serums on Nykaa? –
The study shows that product performance and ingredient transparency are the prime drivers of customer loyalty and repurchase intent. Moreover, focus on before and after results also supports the above result.
2. Do K-beauty serums work as well as they claim to, or are they shallow marketing fads?
The skeptical perception of Korean serums by 60% of the participants and the suspicion that they might be fashionable (36.7%) reflect a degree of skepticism regarding their efficacy.

V. DISCUSSIONS

The results of this research offer significant insights into consumers' buying behavior in the instance of serums on Nykaa in the 18 to 25 years age group. The results indicate significant trends in buying behavior, ingredient preferences, and attitudes towards K-beauty products. The results are consistent with the findings of earlier research that indicate product performance and receptiveness towards ingredients as key drivers of consumer buying behavior. Product performance was cited as a key driver for buying serums by 67% of the participants. This is an increasing trend among consumers to favor performance over brand loyalty, which is consistent with the research conducted by Kim and Kim (2022), who observed that consumers choose products that yield observable outcomes. 51% of the subjects in this study named ingredients as the most important factor before buying a serum, and favored niacinamide, hyaluronic acid, and vitamin C.

Findings of this research on K-beauty serum perceptions are consistent with past research. Regardless of K-beauty being a leading global trend, the fear shown by 60% of the respondents that Korean serums do not work is indicative of a wider trend spotted by researchers such as Kim and Kim (2022), who pointed out that consumer confidence in the effectiveness of K-beauty offerings is still a cause for concern, in spite of being touted as the latest versions. The belief by 36.7% of the respondents that K-beauty serums are trendy further suggests that brands must come up with strong evidence of their effectiveness in order to overcome consumer skepticism.

The implications of these findings for communication strategies are numerous, especially on marketing strategies embraced by beauty companies. Firstly, the focus on product effectiveness and ingredient transparency means that businesses must prioritize more emphasis on open and transparent communication about their products. This involves providing detailed information on the advantage of particular ingredients, in addition to providing before-and-after photos through testimonials and visual presentations. By embracing this approach, brands can build credibility and earn trust among consumers, thereby having a positive influence on their repetition purchase behavior. Secondly, the tilt towards online shopping, as shown by 55% of the respondents, indicates the predominant significance of online marketing efforts that engage with this segment. Businesses should utilize social media platforms and collaborations with influencers to express product messages and interact meaningfully with buyers. Considering that most of the respondents are from a younger age group that is highly technology-savvy, the use of such platforms as Instagram and TikTok for targeted advertisement campaigns can play a crucial function in enhancing brand visibility and consumer interaction.

In addition, K-beauty product skepticism implies that businesses have to incur some expense on educational content in order to mitigate consumers' concerns. With educational content detailing the science behind their products and efficacy of their ingredients, businesses can de-populize Kbeauty and gain a better understanding among consumers. The study has several strengths that contribute to the validity and generalizability of the study. Firstly, the quantitative research design allows the use of quantifiable data, and it is therefore possible to have an actual insight into what consumers do and enjoy. The use of snowball sampling method allowed the study to reach a target population, and the findings are therefore generalizable to the target population. Secondly, the wellstructured online questionnaire allowed effective collection of data so that a thorough understanding of consumers' attitudes towards serums was achieved. However,

the study also has several limitations to be taken into consideration.

The use of self-reported data can be skewed since the respondents may not always provide thoughtful or accurate responses. Furthermore, the use of the snowball sampling method, while effective in reaching a target population, can lead to the samples being too homogenous and thereby skew the findings. The comparison against a single e-retail website, Nykaa, can also further limit generalizability of the conclusions to other buying environments. More sample diversity and further extension of customer behavior to other sites and other population segments are required by follow-up studies.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The objective of this study was to establish the drivers for repeat purchase of Nykaa's customers for serums, especially Korean beauty (Kbeauty) products within the age bracket 18-25. Several findings were established: Most of those responding were described as young females, which represents a very large target market for serum products among this group. A large number of customers (37%) purchase serums every 2-3 months, indicating moderate adoption of serum usage and also indicating brand loyalty. The fact that 55% prefer to purchase serums online indicates the position online shopping portals like Nykaa have reached in the context of shaping consumer behavior. Being successful in product (67%) and ingredient (51%) disclosure were the key features that influenced purchasing decisions, indicating that products need to work and ingredients need to be highly educated about. A large proportion of the respondents (60%) never used Korean serums and reported that they did not feel strongly about their use, 36.7% viewing them as a trend, not a fixture in their skincare regimen.

A strong focus on before and after evidence (57%) indicates that consumers want to witness real evidence of how a product works prior to parting with their money for the same. Findings of this research uncover a number of implications that will prove useful to beauty marketers and brands alike.

Brands need to focus more on creating marketing campaigns that revolve around product performance and visibility for ingredients. The goal can be attained by properly communicating the value of ingredients, using the application of before-and-after results, and leveraging customer reviews.

With rising demand for online shopping, companies stand to gain significantly by increasing their online visibility through influencer marketing, social media campaigns, and content for

the 18-25 age bracket. Instagram and TikTok are now viable channels for advertising, providing consumer segments with access to offers in bulk.

Brands need to invest in content educating consumers about the science behind the products, especially for K-beauty serums. This investment will be used in the battle against skepticism and to win over consumers who are unfamiliar with these types of products.

The knowledge of consumer demand for certain ingredients like niacinamide, hyaluronic acid, and vitamin C can drive product development efforts in a particular direction. Firms can look at the possibility of developing serums from such in-demand ingredients to fulfill consumer demand.

For the sake of building consumer trust and promoting safety within the beauty sector, the below policy recommendations are proposed:

Regulatory agencies should put in place specific guidelines on ingredient labeling behavior of Nykaa customers of serums as the 18-25 age group. The results emanating from this research emphasize the importance of product performance and advertising messages in the cosmetic industry. This will help ensure that consumers are provided with adequate information on the products they buy. Governments and trade associations should promote consumer education schemes to inform consumers about skincare products, their benefits, and making an informed choice appropriate to their needs. Transparency practices should be encouraged by prompting brands to implement transparency practices in their testing, formulation, and sourcing.

This would enable trust among consumers and lead to an educated marketplace. While this study is valuable, there are several areas that need to be studied in greater depth:

Subsequent research could be enriched with a more heterogeneous sample representing various age groups, gender, and socioeconomic levels to be able to capture consumer behaviour across various populations. Comparative analysis of consumer behaviour in various online shopping platforms and physical store platforms can help clarify the role of shopping experiences in shaping purchasing decisions. Longitudinal studies of changes in consumer behaviour and trends over time can help identify new trends and shifts in the beauty sector. Studies that analyze the performance of various marketing activities, including influencer collaborations and social media ad campaigns, can be useful to brands looking to maximize reach. Finally, this research determines the most influential drivers of the repeat purchase ingredient transparency, and online shopping in shaping the purchasing of customers. With

the algorithms, consumer intersection of the practical implications choices are both and policy recommendations espoused in this research, beauty companies can increase their marketing efforts, create confidence among consumers, and ultimately make sales in a competitive market. Future research will be tasked with further examining the changing patterns of consumer behavior within the beauty sector, which will keep companies updated with customers' needs and wants.

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